

Interventions to facilitate long-term travel data collection via smartphones

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ABSTRACT

Smartphone applications used in travel surveys can increasingly detect trip characteristics automatically. However, manual validation and labeling remain necessary, often leading to incomplete data and participant attrition. Continuous incentives – small, frequent rewards for ongoing participation – may improve data completeness by sustaining respondent motivation and engagement. This study examined the effects of economic, gamification, and nudging interventions on the completeness of GPS-based cycling data collected via a mobile app. Three separate time periods with different reward structures were compared: 1) low monetary rewards, 2) high monetary rewards, and 3) gamification elements with nudging applied to a random subset of the sample. Completeness was evaluated using two outcomes: (1) overall trip recording rate and (2) the rate of spatially unchained trips – pairs of recorded trips whose start and end locations did not match, indicating at least one unrecorded trip. Andersen–Gill survival models estimated the change in each outcome during the interventions, adjusting for demographic and behavioral factors. The results indicate that the period with higher economic rewards simultaneously increased the trip recording rate and reduced the rate of unchained trips, indicating improved data completeness as compared to the period with low economic rewards. Gamification significantly reduced the rate of unchained trips but did not increase overall trip recording as compared to the period without gamification, providing only partial evidence of its effectiveness. Nudging had no significant effect on either outcome. These findings contribute to travel behavior research by demonstrating how travel data collection efforts can be improved to incentivize respondent engagement. These findings contribute to travel behavior research by showing how different incentive strategies can improve participant engagement in travel data collection. Methodologically, the study introduces a spatially based approach for assessing the continuity and completeness of GPS-derived travel data.

1. Background

Understanding individuals' travel behavior over extended periods – spanning several days, weeks, months, or even years – is essential for capturing the dynamic nature of mobility patterns. Longitudinal data facilitate the analysis of recurring variations, such as differences between weekdays and weekends or across seasons, and reveal how travel behavior evolves in response to changes in personal circumstances (e.g., residential relocation, life events) and external conditions, including extreme events or crises (Chlond et al., 2024; de Haas et al., 2024). In addition, observing travel behavior changes in response to transport policies or interventions enables evaluation of their real-world effectiveness and long-term impacts (Stopher & Greaves, 2007). Such evidence is vital for informing policies and designing transport systems that are equitable, resilient, and environmentally sustainable.

However, collecting travel data over extended periods presents significant challenges, primarily due to the burden placed on respondents to provide detailed accounts of all their trips, including origins, destinations, travel modes, purposes, and other contextual information. Sustaining respondent engagement over long durations is particularly difficult when using traditional travel diaries, which largely rely on self-reporting and recall (Chlond et al., 2024). These methods are prone to various data quality issues, including a general decline in data quality over the survey period, such as underreporting of trips and inaccuracies in reported times, locations, and distances (Bohte & Maat, 2009; McCool et al., 2021), limiting their value for activity-based modeling and transport policy evaluation.

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1.1. App-based data collection

The widespread adoption of smartphones has facilitated the development of app-based methods for collecting detailed travel diary data. These applications leverage the integrated GPS sensors in smartphones to passively record mobility patterns, reducing reliance on self-reported data. A growing number of such tools have been developed in recent years (e.g., Cottrill et al., 2013; Faghieh Imani et al., 2020; Greaves et al., 2025; Hong et al., 2021; McCool et al., 2021; Safi et al., 2015), and empirical tests suggest that they provide higher quality data compared to traditional travel diaries based on respondents' recall (Hong et al., 2021; Safi et al., 2017). App-based travel surveys offer a promising alternative to long-term data collection, as they are capable of automatically capturing trip attributes such as origin and destination locations and departure and arrival times (Faghieh Imani et al., 2020; McCool et al., 2021). Many also incorporate algorithms to infer travel modes and trip purposes to further reduce respondents' labeling (Cottrill et al., 2013; Hong et al., 2021; Roddis et al., 2019; Safi et al., 2015).

While smartphone-based travel survey apps offer significant advantages in terms of reducing the time required for respondents to complete traditional travel diaries (Roddis et al., 2019), they introduce new forms of respondent burden that can negatively affect participation. A prominent challenge is the high battery consumption associated with continuous GPS tracking, which creates a trade-off between data precision and battery preservation. Excessive battery drain may interfere with users' everyday phone use, discouraging ongoing engagement with the app (Cottrill et al., 2013). Apart from that, being tracked may itself be perceived as a burden or an intrusion of privacy, which may deter participation.

High level of interaction with the app is another challenge for data quality and participation (Safi et al., 2015). For example, Hood et al. (2011) used the CycleTracks app, where the users had to manually indicate the start and end of their trip in order for the app to record the GPS coordinates. This is advantageous in terms of battery consumption but disadvantageous because of the disruptiveness of the app in respondents' travel. Even when location data are collected passively, many applications still rely on participants to validate detected trip characteristics to prevent errors (Cottrill et al., 2013; Faghieh Imani et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2021; McCool et al., 2021; Roddis et al., 2019; Safi et al., 2017). Validation tasks, such as confirming travel modes, adding trip purposes, and correcting misidentified stops, may feel onerous, particularly when repeated daily over extended periods. Evidence suggests that only highly engaged users tend to complete these tasks thoroughly, with many others ignoring the validation interface (Cottrill et al., 2013). In addition, higher validation requirements emerge when the prediction of modes, stops, and purposes results in many errors for the respondents to correct. This was one of the most reported problems with a Future Mobility Sensing travel diary app, e.g., "Although this travel [validation] only took 5 min, initial days took much longer, and occasionally the app missed trips completely", "The app would sometimes put in extra stops or suggest I was in a car when I was on the tram", "Too many non-stops added", and "Validation is difficult when data is not recorded properly." And hard to correct when validating" (Roddis et al., 2019). Such issues may reduce the data quality if the respondents are not motivated (Safi et al., 2015).

1.2. Incentivization strategies

Incentives can be used to encourage participation despite the perceived burden of battery drain and validation/labeling, as they have been an important tool in survey research to motivate participation in general (Abdelazeem et al., 2023) and are reportedly a determining factor in whether individuals decide to take part in a travel survey (Roddis et al., 2019). Incentives can take the form of monetary (e.g., cash, checks, or vouchers) or non-monetary rewards, such as gifts or information (Scheepers & Hoogendoorn-Lanser, 2018). The rewards can

be provided at different times: unconditional incentives are given upfront, while conditional incentives depend on survey completion. For longitudinal data collection, respondents can be rewarded several times during the survey period, possibly with increasing value (Greaves et al., 2025).

App-based data collection offers new opportunities for recurring rewards, as they can automatically track and reward engagement. In this way, continuous incentivization strategies can be used, whereby small, frequent rewards are offered for daily data contributions. This type of incentivization is grounded in Reinforcement theory's continuous reinforcement scheme, where reinforcement is provided every time a target behavior is performed (Ferster & Skinner, 1957). It has a long history of applications across various fields, including education, health, and organizational science (Chudzynski et al., 2015; Hulac et al., 2016; Yuki & Latham, 1975). Particular attention has been devoted to monetary incentives, which have been shown to motivate repeated activities such as physical activity (Berardi et al., 2020), increase performance in a work setting (Pritchard et al., 1980), and support habit formation for exercising (Beshears et al., 2021).

In addition to monetary rewards, apps can also offer more diverse types of non-monetary rewards in the context of gamification. Gamification refers to the application of game design elements in non-game contexts (Deterding et al., 2011). The core premise is to increase motivation for otherwise tedious or effortful tasks by making them more engaging and enjoyable. Game elements such as points, badges, and trophies can function as incentives linked to the completion of specific survey tasks or the achievement of milestones within the gamified system. In this way, both short-term (verifying and labeling trip data each day) and long-term participation (providing data for a certain number of days) can be encouraged. Carefully designed gamification strategies thus have the potential to elicit more complete datasets and extend the duration of data collection (Arakawa & Matsuda, 2016).

As an example, Bricka and Greaves (2018) discussed a gamified mock design for a 7-day household travel survey administered via smartphone by employing existing technologies. Respondents had avatars representing household members and could earn rewards by providing daily data on their travel behavior. To prevent the common decline in participation in the middle of the week and the resulting loss of data, the game rewards were proposed to increase mid-week. To further encourage complete data provision, competition mechanisms between household members were proposed.

While, to our knowledge, there are no available empirical examples for travel surveys, some parallels can be drawn to other high-frequency data collection efforts, such as participatory sensing and experience sampling methodology. Participatory sensing refers to a data collection approach in which individuals voluntarily use their smartphones or other devices to collect data about their environment through GPS, accelerometers, and gyroscopes (Arakawa & Matsuda, 2016). Given the high participant burden, a key challenge is maintaining sustained engagement from participants over time. Preliminary empirical evidence for the effectiveness of gamification to support participatory sensing was presented by Ueyama et al. (2014). The study spanned over 30 days and included 18 participants, who were required to use a smartphone application to visit designated points of interest and complete sensing tasks assigned by the app. Participants could earn reward points, which were convertible to money, through two randomized types of requests: 1) requests with both monetary and gamification incentives and requests with only monetary incentives. The gamified incentives included a status-level system, where higher accumulated points increased reward earnings; a ranking system to encourage competition; and a badge system. The study found that participants were more likely to complete requests that included gamification features compared to those with only monetary incentives.

Despite the preliminary evidence of gamification's effectiveness in high-burden data collection (Arakawa & Matsuda, 2016; Ueyama et al., 2014) and the recognition of its potential value for travel surveys (Bricka

& Greaves, 2018; Masso et al., 2025), gamified travel surveys have, to our knowledge, not been quantitatively evaluated yet. Thus, it remains unclear whether gamification is a viable incentivization strategy to motivate survey participation over longer periods and whether it has an added value in addition to continuous economic incentives. And while incentives are an important tool, the effects of alternative strategies that smartphones enable, such as motivational messages, should also be considered, as previous research suggests that they are a valuable complement to incentives (Griffith Fillipo et al., 2022).

1.3. Research objectives

The aim of the study was to assess the value of different interventions to motivate participants' engagement with long-term app-based travel surveys. Three types of interventions were evaluated with respect to their effect on trip underreporting: 1) continuous economic incentives; 2) continuous gamified incentives (non-economic); and 3) nudging messages that did not rely on rewards, as the former two did.

The interventions were applied in different periods to allow for within- and between-subject comparisons. The following alternative hypotheses were tested while controlling for sociodemographic factors, self-reported mobility behavior, and satisfaction with the app:

- Hypothesis 1 (H1): The period with higher economic rewards will decrease the risk of unrecorded trips compared to the period with lower economic rewards.
- Hypothesis 2 (H2): The period with gamification elements will decrease the risk of unrecorded trips compared to the period without gamification elements.
- Hypothesis 3 (H3). Users randomized to receive nudging messages decrease the risk of unrecorded trips compared to users in the control group who did not receive them.

Prior research has emphasized that preferences for incentives can vary significantly across demographic and behavioral groups, underscoring the importance of tailoring incentivization strategies to specific populations (Svaboe et al., 2025). To contribute to this understanding, we conducted exploratory analyses of interaction effects to identify whether specific subgroups responded particularly positively or negatively to each intervention.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. The methods are presented in Section 2, along with the study setting and a detailed description of the interventions, the data, and the statistical analysis. Section 3 presents the results from the study, which is followed by a discussion that concludes with key takeaways in Section 4.

2. Methods

This evaluation was conducted within the context of the Bike2Green project in Stockholm, Sweden, spanning over a year and a half between 2024 and 2025 (Bike2Green, 2025). The project aimed to promote the adoption of daily cycling through a system of reward-based incentives and gamification. For this reason, the project only collected data on cycling trips, in contrast to general travel surveys that contain all transport modes.

2.1. Recruitment and participation process

Participants were recruited on a rolling basis via posts on social media, posters, and newsletters. To participate, interested individuals had to 1) fill out a registration survey, 2) be at least 13 years of age, 3) have a residential or work address within the Stockholm region, and 4) collect a bike kit and register in the mobile app.

The data collection employed the patented system of Pin Bike (Pin Bike, 2025). It consisted of a mobile application the participants interacted with and a sensor from the kit to be attached to the wheel hub. To

record trip data, participants logged the start and end of the trip in the app, while the sensor validated that the trip was made by bike (instead of by car or e-scooter, for example).

The reliance on manual logging of the start and end of the trip predisposed people to underreporting trips, as forgetting or being in a rush prevented people from interacting with the app before the start of their trip. This was repeatedly reported in a survey about satisfaction with the app (e.g., "Sometimes I am in a hurry to go to work, then it takes some time in the app to detect the sensor and start recording. So then I just don't do it" and "easy to forget to start and end a session"). Thus, the premise is that interventions that increase participant motivation should reduce trip underreporting due to such factors.

2.2. Study design

Economic, gamification, and nudging interventions were applied via the app throughout the study during different periods. For an overview of the interventions and their different study periods, see Table 1.

2.2.1. Economic incentives

Throughout the study period, different reward rules were applied. At the start of the data collection, users could earn 2 Swedish crowns (SEK) per km for commute trips (trips between home and work/study location) and 1 SEK per km for any other trip (Period 1, P1).¹ The rewards per person could not exceed 40 SEK (3.6 EUR) per day and 330 SEK (30 EUR) per month. In addition to this, there was a monthly reward of 220 SEK (20 EUR) for the top forty participants in a monthly ranking. After about 6 months, the economic rewards were increased to 5 SEK and 2 SEK per km for commute and non-commute trips, respectively (Period 2, P2); the daily limit was increased to 100 SEK (9 EUR), the monthly limit to 550 SEK (50 EUR), and the monthly reward for the top users was increased to 300 SEK (27 EUR).

2.2.2. Gamification

Throughout the whole study period, points were awarded for different desirable behaviors, including cycled kilometers, filling out surveys, inviting users to the project, or joining a specified cycling event in Stockholm. The points determined the position of the user in monthly rankings, from which the top users received an additional economic reward.

Table 1

An overview of the applied interventions with their design and test periods.

Intervention and hypothesis	Design	Period	Timeframe (dd.mm.yyyy)	Duration
Monetary incentives (H1)	Within-subject	Low	Period 1 (P1) 01.08.2024 – 01.09.2024	4 weeks
		High	Period 2 (P2) 02.09.2024 – 29.09.2024 ^a	4 weeks
Gamification (H2)	Within-subject	No gamification	Period 2 (P2) 02.09.2024 – 29.09.2024	4 weeks
Challenges + Trophies		Period 3 (P3) 30.09.2024 – 22.12.2024 ^b	12 weeks ^b	
Nudging (H3)	Between-subject	Period 4 (P4) 03.10.2024 – 01.11.2024		4 weeks

^a The high monetary rewards were kept for the remaining duration of the project but only the indicated period was compared to the lower rewards.

^b The gamification period ended when a participant earned a gold trophy which happened at different times for each participant (if at all) but at the latest on 22.12.2024.

¹ 1 SEK corresponds to 0,091 Euro.

In the gamification period (Period 3), several additional gamification elements were added: weekly challenges, trophies (with progress bars), a monthly lottery, a trip log wall, and location prizes. The weekly challenges set cycling-related goals, such as achieving a specific number of kilometers or completing a certain number of trips within a week, which were based on the previous months of cycling activity. To accommodate participants with different goals, several difficulty levels were established (Table 2). Each week there was a mix of easy, moderate, or hard challenges so that every participant had potentially something to strive for. All users were automatically enrolled in all active challenges. Upon reaching the target, participants received a congratulatory message and earned points as a reward.

In addition, long-term objectives were defined for a 12-week period, informed by prior project data, with progress monitored through progress bars. These objectives comprised three sequential distance-based milestones, denoted by bronze, silver, and gold trophies (Table 2).

In addition to those goal-based elements, there was a lottery that randomly assigned points to users with moderate cycling activity to promote their striving for the monthly ranking. Approximately once per month the participants could also earn a prize in points if they attended a cycling event in the city. The log wall offered information about trips that Bike2Green participants took, including duration, distance, and corresponding rewards. The aim was to make cycling in the community more salient and induce peer influence.

2.2.3. Nudging

The nudging intervention involved sending weekly messages through the app's notification system during period 4 (P4). It was the only between-subject intervention, for which a simple random sample of the activated users was drawn as the intervention group, and the remaining users were the control group. Both the control and intervention groups received three general messages, including information about the project and a survey prompt. The intervention group received one additional message every week over 4 weeks (Table 3). These messages were designed such that they cover aspects of the Self-Determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 1985). These included 1) promoting a feeling of relatedness, 2) relating cycling to a sense of autonomy, and 3) highlighting benefits of cycling that contribute to society. One message included local information about cycling infrastructure developments. The messages balanced general content, such as the benefits of cycling, with specific information and calls to action, such as inviting a friend to a cycling course.

2.3. Data

The data utilized in the analyses included survey data, as well as trip characteristics and GPS data collected through the app. Data collected until December 2024 was considered in the analyses.

2.3.1. Survey data

A registration survey was filled out by all participants and collected data on socio-demographic factors and mobility behavior. Age was

Table 2

Short- and long-term goals, as represented by weekly challenges and trophies, and their targets, respectively.

Element	Target (km)	Target (# trips)
Weekly challenges		
Easy	15	4
Medium	25	—
Hard	40	8
Extra hard	60	—
Trophies		
Bronze	0—75	—
Silver	75—250	—
Gold	250—500	—

Table 3

Messages received by the nudging group, together with the notification title and aim of the message.

Target	Title*	Message
Relatedness	Building cycling community!	Do you know someone who could commute by bike? Encourage them to give it a try! Bike2Green offers free bike rentals and cycling training for beginners and those looking to boost their confidence in city cycling.
Extrinsic regulation & autonomy	Trust your bike!	Have you ever been late because of congestion or irregular public transport? Cycling is more reliable than other modes – you're less likely to be unexpectedly delayed!
Identified regulation & competence	Towards a better city!	The more people cycle, the less pollution and congestion will there be in Stockholm. You make the city a better place when you cycle!
Local information	Stockholm's cycling infrastructure	The City of Stockholm has invested billions in improving the city's cycling infrastructure. Did you know you can see both completed and planned projects online? You can check here: https://vaxer.stockholm/projekt/?typ=filter&kategori=574 ?

*as displayed to the users in the app.

determined from the date of birth, and gender was classified into “Male”, “Female” and “Other” from a multiple-choice question with an additional free-text field. An additional survey administered 4 months after the start of the project (from now on referred to as the Mid-term survey) inquired about the current mobility behavior and satisfaction with the project. Cycling frequency was determined from the question “How often do you use the following modes of transport currently for your daily routine activities (e.g., commuting to work/school) in a regular week (NOT weekends or holidays)?”, which was rated on a 5-point Likert scale question with the response options “(almost) never”, “a few times per month”, “1–2 times per week”, “3–4 times per week”, and “daily.” Participant satisfaction with the app was determined from the question “How satisfied are you with the Pin Bike app overall?” and was rated on a 5-point Likert scale with responses “Very dissatisfied”, “Dissatisfied”, “Neutral”, “Satisfied”, “Very satisfied”, with the addition of an “I cannot tell” response. Both surveys were available in Swedish and English.

2.3.2. Trip data and unrecorded trips

Data on each trip was provided by Pin Bike and included the date, timestamp of the start and end of the trip, distance, and the GPS trajectories, including a string of latitude-longitude pairs. The data was pre-processed to resolve errors such as accidental logs, when participants unintentionally started a trip in the app, resulting in short trips in duration and distance (see section inclusion criteria). Aberrant GPS trajectories were present in the data (such as straight lines across the city), but no actions were taken to process or filter them since the whole trajectories are not used in the analyses, but only the start and end locations were extracted to identify unrecorded trips.

An unrecorded trip was defined as a trip that occurred between two consecutive reported trips for which the end location of the former trip was not the start location of the latter trip (from now on referred to as spatially unchained trips). The start and end locations of each recorded trip were extracted from the GPS trajectories. Then, for each pair of consecutive trips, it was determined whether the end location of the former trip coincided (with a buffer of 300 m to account for GPS location inaccuracies) with the start location of the latter trip. If yes, the two trips were considered chained, and it was assumed that no unrecorded trip took place. Instead, if the trips were not chained, it was assumed that the person did at least one bike trip between the end of the former and the

start of the latter trip but did not record it. This definition of unrecorded trips implies that the participant is generally able to record trips (i.e., there are no technical issues) and willing to do so, as they logged on a trip after the unrecorded trip(s). The limitations of this approach are discussed in Section 4.

2.3.3. Inclusion criteria

Data collected between the start of the project and December 22, 2024, were considered in the current analyses. All users had to have filled out the Mid-term survey, as data on satisfaction and up-to-date self-reported cycling frequency are key covariates. Only trips that started or ended in Region Stockholm were considered. Trips that were shorter than 1 min and 300 m were considered accidental logs and were removed. For each hypothesis, only users who had at least five trips in each relevant period were included. Table 4 presents an overview of the inclusion criteria.

2.3.4. Risk of unrecorded trips

The risk of unrecorded trips, which is the outcome of interest in the current study, is unknown and unobservable. In particular, it is not trivial to distinguish whether a trip was made and not reported or no trip was made, an issue that has been highlighted in other longitudinal travel surveys such as the German Mobility Panel (Chlond et al., 2024). While it is possible to infer the occurrence of at least one unrecorded trip when two consecutive recorded trips are spatially unchained, the precise number and timing of these missing trips cannot be determined. Consequently, the information we can extract about unrecorded trips is highly contingent on both the frequency and sequencing of the recorded trips. For instance, if a participant records only a few sporadic trips, our understanding of the unrecorded trips is limited to what can be deduced from these isolated observations. Conversely, if a participant consistently records every second trip, we obtain a nearly complete picture of the entire travel sequence.

To infer about changes in the risk of unrecorded trips following an intervention, two observed indicators can be used: 1) the “risk” of trip recording in general, related to the frequency of trip recording, and 2) the risk of starting a trip that was not chained to the previous trip, an indicator of the completeness of trip chains. Conclusive evidence of reduced risk of unrecorded trips was considered present if and only if the risk of trip recording increased and the risk of starting an unchained trip decreased.

Notably, each condition is insufficient on its own. For example, the risk of unchained trips would be low not only if people consistently record most of their trips but also if people instead record only a few trips. Since the detection of unchained trips depended on recorded trips, few recorded trips would only give information about few unchained trips. Thus, it had to be ensured that the decreased risk of unchained trips was not associated with the decreased rate of trip recording in general. On the other hand, an increased rate of trip recording would not only occur when people provide more complete accounts of their trips but also if they generally make more trips, but without consideration of

Table 4
Overview of the inclusion criteria.

Applicability	Inclusion criteria
All participants	Registered before 22 December 2024 Completed the Mid-term survey
All trips	Trips made before 22 December 2024 Trips that start and end in Stockholm region Trips longer than 300 m Trips longer than 1 min
Hypothesis 1 (money)	Participants with at least 5 trips during P1 Participants with at least 5 trips during P2
Hypothesis 2 (gamification)	Participants with at least 5 trips during P2 Participants with at least 5 trips during P3 Not randomized into the nudging intervention
Hypothesis 3 (nudging)	Participants with at least 5 trips during P4

how complete data they provide on their travel.

2.3.5. Statistical analysis

To evaluate the impact of interventions on the risk of unrecorded trips, we analyzed how the occurrence of trip recording in general and the occurrence of unchained trips changed in the intervention compared to the respective control conditions. The intensity of occurrence of each type of trip was modeled with the Andersen–Gill (AG) extension of the Cox proportional hazards model (Andersen & Gill, 1982). The AG model uses the times of recurrent events for each subject to model their intensity of occurrence $\lambda_i(t)$, i.e., the instantaneous incidence of a new event at a specific time t for a person i , given the multiplicative effect of a set of (possibly time-dependent) covariates: $X_i(t)$

$$\lambda_i(t) = \lambda_0(t)e^{\beta X_i(t)}$$

where $\lambda_0(t)$ is the baseline intensity function that represents the intensity of occurrence when the covariates are at their reference levels, akin to the intercept in regression models. The coefficient in the vector β indicate the effect of the respective covariate on the intensity of event occurrence. The AG model is suited for analysis of frequent events when the objective is to estimate the overall influence of covariates on the intensity of occurrence (Amorim & Cai, 2015; Thenmozhi et al., 2019), such as the intervention effects in this study.

All effects were reported as hazard ratios (HR), which are the exponents of the coefficients of the AG model. They indicate to what extent the intensity of occurrence is changed by changing the values on the covariate (Amorim & Cai, 2015). HR = 1 indicates no effect, HR < 1 a reduction in intensity of occurrence for higher values of the predictor, and HR > 1 an increase in intensity of recurrence for higher values of the predictor. For example, if an experimental and control group are compared with resulting $HR_{\text{experimental}} = 0.70$, the interpretation is that the intensity of occurrence for the experimental group is 0.70 times as high as the intensity of occurrence for the control group. This can also be interpreted in terms of instantaneous risk: the risk of an event occurring at any given instant is 30% lower in the experimental group compared to the control group.

We concluded there is support for the stated hypotheses if the intensity of occurrence of trip recording significantly increased and the intensity of occurrence (or instantaneous risk) of unchained trips significantly decreased when comparing the interventions to their respective control conditions, as indicated by their coefficients. The Type I error rate was fixed at 5%.

The AG model assumes independence of time increments between recurrent events conditional on covariates. This implies that the covariates account for all sources of dependence. If the assumption is violated, the implication is that standard errors will be underestimated and the Type I error inflated. In this study, subject-specific dependence is expected but cannot be directly controlled for. This was addressed in two ways in the analysis. First, by including a time-varying number of recorded and unrecorded trips and, thus, capturing subject-specific travel history. Second, a sandwich estimate of the variance–covariance matrix was used to provide robust standard errors and 95% confidence intervals (Amorim & Cai, 2015).

The AG model also assumes proportional hazards (PH), i.e., that the covariates have a constant effect on the intensity of occurrence over time. The assumption was tested by comparing the PH model for each predictor with an alternative model in which the predictor’s regression coefficient was permitted to vary over time (Grambsch & Therneau, 1994). If the test was significant, i.e., there was evidence of non-proportionality, the HP assumption was relaxed by interacting the respective predictor with time (Nahhas, 2025). Visual inspection of the scaled Schoenfeld residuals against time indicated whether the coefficient varied linearly with time or a nonlinear function of time was more appropriate, e.g., as a logarithm or polynomial.

All analyses were performed in R (version 4.3.1, R Core Team, 2024).

The GPS data was processed with the *sf* package (version 1.0.19, Pebesma, 2018). The AG model was implemented with the R package *survival* (version 3.5–8, Therneau, 2024).

3. Results

3.1. Sample selection

By the end of the period analyzed in the current study, 2770 individuals filled out the registration form and were thus recruited into the project. Of these, 1155 (42%) actually participated by collecting their bike kit and registering in the Pin Bike app. Only 399 of those (35%) filled out the Mid-term survey and were included in the analyses. After removing trips that were too short in distance or duration and made outside the study area (4%), the sample was reduced to 396 participants who recorded 50,620 trips (Fig. 1). The dataset analyzed for each hypothesis was further limited by the number of trips made per participant, ranging from N = 137 to N = 303, with trips between 8525 and 11439.

3.2. Sample characteristics

Table 5 presents the demographic characteristics of participants corresponding to each analysis. Across all analyses, there were more men than women, and only a few individuals classified themselves as neither man nor woman. In addition, the sample was dominated by frequent cyclists, who reported in the Mid-term survey that they cycle at least 1–2 times per week. The mean age of participants was consistent across all datasets (M = 38; SD = 10). Overall satisfaction with the application was moderately positive (M = 3.3, SD = 1.1, on a 5-point Likert scale).

Trip recording varied between weekdays and weekends, across periods, and to some extent with seasonal changes (Fig. 2). There were

Table 5
Descriptive statistics of the samples analyzed for each hypothesis.

	Money	Gamification	Nudging control group	nudging group
<i>N</i>	204	137	157	146
<i>Gender</i>				
Female	71	48	60	51
Male	130	88	95	93
Other	3	1	2	2
Age: Mean (SD)	38.2 (9.8)	39 (10.7)	38.4 (10.7)	37.3 (9.3)
<i>Self-reported bike frequency</i>				
Never or almost never	0	1	1	0
A few times per month	1	0	1	1
1–2 times per week	15	9	9	11
3–4 times per week	61	41	42	43
Daily	127	86	104	91
Satisfaction with app: Mean (SD)	3.2 (1.1)	3.3 (1.1)	3.3 (1.1)	3.2 (1.1)

fewer trips on the weekends than on weekdays. The total trips per day for the sample showed an increasing trend until the middle of Period 3, when they started decreasing. This coincided with a period of lower temperatures that oscillated around 0°C. Nevertheless, the transition from summer to winter in the months before did not seem to covary with the trip recording pattern.

3.3. Intervention effects

3.3.1. Economic incentives

The analysis of the effect of increased economic incentives during P2 on the intensity of occurrence of unchained trips and trip recording, in

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of the included participants according to the inclusion criteria of each hypothesis.

Fig. 2. Variation of average temperature and number of recorded trips per day. The colored background areas labelled with P1-P4 correspond to the duration of each test period, from Period 1 to Period 4.

general, compared to P1 provided results consistent with H1 (Model 1.1 and Model 1.2, Table 6). The intensity of unchained trips during P2 was 0.78 times the intensity during P1, while controlling for confounding factors ($p = 0.028$). That is, P2 was associated with a reduced instantaneous risk of unchained trips of 22% compared to P1. In addition, the intensity of occurrence of recorded trips significantly increased ($HR = 1.34, p < 0.001$). In sum, these two findings suggest that participants recorded trips more often, and these were more often chained in P2 compared to P1, limiting the possibilities of unrecorded trips and providing support for Hypothesis 1.

Models 2.1 and 2.2 (Table 6) explored whether the higher economic incentives during P2 were particularly (in)effective for certain subgroups by including interactions of P2 with gender, age, self-reported bike frequency, and satisfaction. However, none of the interactions

were significant, implying that the effect of P2 did not vary for people with different characteristics.

3.3.2. Gamification

H2 regarding the effect of gamification on the intensity of occurrence of unrecorded trips was only partly empirically supported (Models 3.1 and 3.2, Table 7). The intensity of unchained trips during P3 (with gamification) was 0.59 times the one during P2 ($p < 0.001$), while adjusting for confounding factors. This indicates a 41% reduction in the instantaneous risk of unchained trips associated with the gamification phase relative to the prior period without gamification. However, there was only a descriptive increase in intensity of occurrence of recorded trips, which was not significant ($HR = 1.08, p = 0.32$), which was the second condition that was necessary to conclusively support the

Table 6

AG models on the effect of increased monetary incentives during P2 on risk of unchained trips and trip recording compared the period with lower incentives during P1.

Model outcome	Hypothesis testing (H1)				Exploratory analysis			
	Model 1.1 Intensity of occurrence of unchained trips		Model 1.2 Intensity of occurrence of trip recording		Model 2.1 Intensity of occurrence of unchained trips		Model 2.2 Intensity of occurrence of trip recording	
Predictor	HR	p	HR	p	HR	p	HR	p
Monetary incentive: P2	0.78	0.028	1.34	0<.001	0.58	0.040	1.30	0.080
# Unchained trips	1.05	<0.001	1.00	0.628	1.05	<0.001	1.00	0.645
# Trips	1.00 ^a	<0.001	1.01	0<.001	1.00 ^a	<0.001	1.01	0<.001
Gender								
male	1.07	0.376	1.03	0.547	1.03	0.711	1.03	0.614
other	1.30	0.069	0.91	0.473	1.26	0.067	0.79	0.004
Age	1.00	0.248	1.00	0.058	1.00	0.822	1.00	0.435
Bike frequency								
3–4 times/week	0.94	0.744	1.04	0.679	0.93	0.737	1.00	0.996
Daily	1.15	0.407	1.21	0.060	1.16	0.454	1.25	0.070
Satisfaction	0.97	0.366	1.02	0.353	0.95	0.165	1.02	0.381
Time since joined	0.99	<0.001	0.99	0<.001	0.99	<0.001	0.99	0<.001
Monetary incentive: P2 × Gender								
× Male	—	—			1.08	0.542	1.00	0.961
× Other	—	—			1.09	0.648	1.29	0.015
Money × Age	—	—			1.01	0.138	1.00	0.412
Monetary incentive: P2 × Bike frequency								
× 3–4 times/week	—	—			1.03	0.903	1.09	0.545
× Daily	—	—			0.99	0.966	0.94	0.640
Money × Satisfaction	—	—			1.04	0.424	0.99	0.842

N = 203, total trips = 11549, total unrecorded trips = 1798; age was centered at the lowest age in the sample (16 years); Satisfaction ranged from 0 to 4; The baseline intensity function is for a female individual during P1, with 0 recorded and unchained trips, at the age of 16 years, with self-reported bike frequency of 1–2 times per week, very dissatisfied with the project and just joined the project (i.e. time since joined is 0 days).

^a Rounded from 0.997; Abbreviations: CI – confidence interval, P – Period; p – p-value.

Table 7

AG models on the effect of gamification during P3 on risk of unchained trips (Models 3.1 and 3.3) and trip recording (Models 3.2 and 4.2) compared to the P2.

Model outcome Predictor	Hypothesis testing (H2)				Exploratory analysis			
	Model 3.1 Intensity of occurrence of unchained trips		Model 3.2 Intensity of occurrence of trip recording		Model 4.1 Intensity of occurrence of unchained trips		Model 4.2 Intensity of occurrence of trip recording	
	HR	p	HR	p	HR	p	HR	p
Gamification (P3)	0.59	<0.001	1.08	0.315	0.43	0.041	0.77	0.304
# Unchained trips	1.04	<0.001	1.00	0.628	1.04	<0.001	1.00	0.608
# Trips	1.00	0.145	1.01	0<.001	1.00	0.143	1.01	0<.001
Gender								
male	1.06	0.585	0.98	0.759	1.30	0.077	1.02	0.854
other	1.62	0.011	1.33	0.002	1.76	0.005	1.31	0.019
Age	0.98	0.168	1.00	0.954	0.98	0.138	1.00	0.681
Bike frequency								
3–4 times/week	1.22	0.272	1.25	0.207	0.93	0.748	1.16	0.435
Daily	1.55	0.017	1.53	0.017	1.19	0.395	1.37	0.084
Satisfaction	0.96	0.376	1.03	0.263	0.96	0.529	1.02	0.719
Time since joined	0.99	<0.001	0.99	0<.001	0.99	<0.001	0.99	0<.001
Age x log(time)	1.01	0.022	1.00	0.243	1.01	0.028	1.00	0.825
Gamification (P3) × Gender								
× Male	—	—			0.69	0.023	0.94	0.561
× Other	—	—			1.05	0.788	1.04	0.660
Gamification (P3) × Age	—	—			1.00	0.808	1.01	0.169
Gamification (P3) × Bike frequency								
× 3–4 times/week	—	—			1.85	0.035	1.16	0.470
× Daily	—	—			1.87	0.032	1.23	0.291
Gamification (P3) × Satisfaction	—	—			1.00	0.983	1.03	0.527

Abbreviations: CI – confidence interval; N = 136, trips = 8631, unrecorded = 1399; age was centered at the lowest age in the sample (16 years); Satisfaction ranged from 0 to 4; The baseline intensity function is for a female individual during P1, with 0 recorded and unchained trips, at the age of 16 years, with self-reported bike frequency of 1–2 times per week, very dissatisfied with the project and just joined the project (i.e. time since joined is 0 days).

hypothesis. Thus, participants tended to have more chained trips but not more trips in general during P3 compared to P2.

In Model 4.1 (Table 7), a significant interaction between gamification and gender suggested that the reduction in risk of unchained trips during P3 was more pronounced for men than for women (HR = 0.69, p = 0.023), resulting in a total of 70% reduction in risk for men (HR_{men} = 0.43*0.69 = 0.30). Significant interactions emerged also between gamification and bike frequency, with higher HR for those cycling 3–4 times per week (HR = 1.85, p = 0.035) and daily (HR = 1.87, p = 0.032).

These interactions implied that the gamification intervention was not effective among more frequent cyclists, as the interactions resulted in insignificant coefficients (HR = 0.80, p = 0.52 and p = 0.48, respectively). No significant interaction effects were observed in Model 4.2, indicating that no subgroups responded to gamification by recording significantly more or fewer trips. The proportional hazards assumption was violated for age in Models 3.1 and 4.1, which was resolved by interacting age with the logarithm of age.

Table 8

AG model on the effect of nudging (Period 4) on risk of unchained trips (models 5.1 and 6.1) and trip recording (models 5.2 and 6.2) compared to the control group.

Model outcome Predictor	Hypothesis testing (H3)				Exploratory analysis			
	Model 5.1 Intensity of occurrence of unchained trips		Model 5.2 Intensity of occurrence of trip recording		Model 6.1 Intensity of occurrence of unchained trips		Model 6.2 Intensity of occurrence of trip recording	
	HR	p	HR	p	HR	p	HR	p
Nudging group	0.99	0.943	1.03	0.549	3.79	0.009	1.09	0.768
# Unchained trips	1.04	<0.001	1.00	0.461	1.04	<0.001	1.00	0.581
# Trips	1.00^a	0.033	1.00	0<.001	1.00^a	0.019	1.00	0<.001
Gender								
male	0.93	0.354	1.08	0.151	0.91	0.402	1.04	0.634
other	0.84	0.519	1.15	0.301	1.51	0.001	1.31	0<.001
Age	1.00	0.567	1.01	0.020	1.01	0.113	1.01	0.027
Bike frequency								
3–4 times/week	1.15	0.590	1.01	0.950	2.91	0.003	0.96	0.772
Daily	1.95	0.007	1.38	0<.001	4.04	<0.001	1.28	0.101
Satisfaction	0.96	0.359	1.03	0.188	0.96	0.407	1.05	0.202
Time since joined	0.99	<0.001	0.99	0<.001	0.99	<0.001	0.99	0<.001
Nudging group × Gender								
× Male	—	—			1.07	0.696	1.09	0.417
× Other	—	—			0.34	<0.001	0.70	0.126
Nudging group × Age	—	—			0.98	0.054	0.99	0.201
Nudging group × Bike frequency								
× 3–4 times/week	—	—			0.24	0.003	1.07	0.710
× Daily	—	—			0.36	0.021	1.14	0.480
Nudging group × Satisfaction	—	—			1.01	0.860	0.97	0.560

Abbreviations: CI – confidence interval, HR – hazard ratio; N = 300, trips = 8573, unrecorded = 1187; age was centered at the lowest age in the sample (16 years); Satisfaction ranged from 0 to 4; The baseline intensity function is for a female individual during P1, with 0 recorded and unchained trips, at the age of 16 years, with self-reported bike frequency of 1–2 times per week, very dissatisfied with the project and just joined the project (i.e. time since joined is 0 days).

^a Rounded from 0.998.

3.3.3. Nudging

The analyses of the effect of nudging messages on the intensity of occurrence of unchained trips and trip recording did not support Hypothesis 3 (Models 5.1 and 5.2, Table 8). Neither was the risk of unchained trips lower in the nudging group ($HR = 0.99, p = 0.94$), nor was the intensity of occurrence of trip recording higher compared to the control group ($HR = 1.03, p = 0.55$). These findings suggest that receiving motivational messages about cycling had no statistically significant effect on participants' trip recording behavior, either in terms of quantity or sequencing.

However, exploratory analyses of the interactions showed that the effect of nudging on the risk of unchained trips was moderated by gender and self-reported bike frequency (Model 6.1, Table 8). Nudging for women reporting they cycle 1–2 times per week seemed to be not only ineffective compared to the control group, but in fact, significantly increased the risk of unrecorded trips ($HR = 3.79, p < 0.009$). The effect was similar for men, given that there was no significant interaction between men and the nudging group. The nudging messages significantly reduced the risk of unrecorded trips only for people who did not identify as male or female and reported cycling 3–4 times per week ($HR = 3.79 \times 0.34 \times 0.24 = 0.31, p = 0.001$) and daily ($HR = 3.79 \times 0.34 \times 0.36 = 0.50, p = 0.015$). However, very few people were in this group, so the results are likely due to chance. There were no significant interactions for the effect of nudging on the intensity of occurrence of recorded trips.

4. Discussion

Despite advances in automatic detection of trips, modes, and travel purposes via smartphone apps, a certain level of participant burden persists because of necessary manual validation and labeling or technical issues such as battery drain (Roddie et al., 2019; Thomas et al., 2018). To mitigate such challenges and motivate sustained engagement with a long-term travel survey, different intervention strategies can be considered. This study aimed to assess whether three types of interventions could motivate participants' engagement with app-based travel surveys over an extended period: 1) continuous economic incentives, 2) continuous gamified incentives (non-economic), and 3) nudging messages that did not rely on rewards.

We found conclusive evidence that continuous economic rewards were effective in reducing trip underreporting. Specifically, higher economic incentives were associated with a decreased risk of unchained trips and an increased intensity of occurrence of trip reporting overall. Exploratory analyses further indicated that these effects were consistent across different age groups, genders, and mobility behavior profiles—distinguishing economic incentives from the gamification and nudging interventions, whose effectiveness varied across subgroups. One possible explanation for this difference is that economic rewards allow participants to utilize them in ways that align with their preferences. In this sense, such incentives may enhance perceived autonomy by enabling individuals to assign value to the rewards themselves, thereby reinforcing motivation in a self-directed manner.

An important caveat comes from the perspective of Self-Determination Theory, according to which economic incentives may have adverse effects when perceived as controlling, as they can undermine individuals' sense of autonomy and reduce intrinsic motivation, particularly when small rewards are offered for simple, repetitive tasks (Thibault Landry et al., 2017). Conversely, incentives can improve motivation when framed as tokens of appreciation, serving as positive feedback that reinforces behavior. In our sample, which consisted primarily of regular cyclists, it is possible that the economic rewards were interpreted as acknowledgments of their ongoing efforts, thereby fostering a sense of appreciation and encouraging reciprocation through consistent trip recording. Thus, when providing economic rewards in the context of general travel surveys, careful consideration should be given to the framing, perceived value, and target audience of the incentive design to ensure that rewards support rather than hinder participants'

intrinsic motivation and engagement.

Incorporating gamification elements could be considered as one of the approaches to frame monetary incentives as positive feedback rather than as a means of control. However, the present study provided inconclusive evidence regarding the overall effectiveness of gamification on trip recording behavior. On the one hand, gamification substantially reduced the risk of unchained trips. On the other hand, it did not lead to an increase in the overall intensity of the occurrence of trip recordings. That is, while participants were more likely to record trips consecutively, the rate of trip recording in general remained unchanged. A plausible explanation for this outcome is that participants were motivated by the goals associated with weekly challenges or trophies and reported more complete trip chains, possibly associated with higher trip recording rates. However, once these goals were achieved, participants may have ceased to record some of their trips in a sequence, which would reduce the trip recording rate but will not increase the rate of unchained trips. This highlights the possibility that goal-based incentivization may reduce motivation after the goals are achieved.

The effectiveness of gamification is further nuanced by the presence of significant interaction effects, suggesting that its positive impact on trip chaining was not uniform across all participant groups. These disparities may stem from the differential perceived value of gamified "rewards," such as achieving weekly goals or earning trophies, among various subgroups. The most notable interaction effect indicated that gamification did not enhance trip chaining behavior among the most frequent cyclists, in contrast to its effects on less frequent cyclists. One possible explanation is that frequent cyclists were able to meet the goals embedded in the gamification framework without modifying their existing trip recording behaviors. Moreover, due to their higher travel frequency, the effort required to consistently record each trip was likely substantially greater for these participants compared to those who traveled less frequently. The perceived value of the gamified rewards was possibly not sufficiently high to incentivize improvements in trip recording behavior.

This issue has important implications for the design of incentive-based interventions in general travel surveys. Specifically, individuals who travel extensively face a higher burden in terms of data validation, trip labeling, and increased battery consumption on mobile devices. As such, the more an individual travels, the greater the participation burden becomes, potentially limiting the overall effectiveness and equity of the incentivization strategy. Thus, on the one hand, we might want to provide rewards contingent on effort, e.g., the more actions are performed in a survey, the more rewards. However, this strategy would be undesirable because it may induce unnecessary travel that otherwise would not have happened. This is particularly problematic, since travel surveys try to capture the travel patterns without influencing them (Bricka & Greaves, 2018).

To mitigate issues with incentivization, interventions that do not rely on incentives can be considered, such as nudging messages. However, the implementation of nudging in the current study did not demonstrate any measurable added value in mitigating underreporting. In fact, the interaction analyses identified subgroups for which being in the nudging group was associated with increased risk of unchained trips, e.g., for people who reported they cycle 1–2 times per day. This subgroup possibly perceived the nudging messages as excessive or irrelevant, thereby reducing their effectiveness. Conversely, more frequent cyclists may have found the messages more relatable and thus experienced less negative impact. These findings suggest that while messages can serve as useful reminders to engage with the app, their effectiveness depends heavily on perceived relevance. To optimize impact, care should be taken to avoid excessive or generic communication that may be regarded as a nuisance.

This study is subject to several limitations that constrain the generalizability of its findings regarding the effectiveness of the tested interventions in promoting engagement in broader travel surveys. First, the scope of data collection was limited to cycling trips, with

participants required to manually initiate and terminate trip recordings. As such, the observed effects may be specific to these user actions. In recent travel survey applications, participant burden is shifted toward tasks such as trip verification, mode and purpose labeling, and increased battery consumption. It remains unclear whether the intervention effects identified in this study would hold under these alternative conditions. Future research should investigate the implementation of continuous incentives within general travel surveys to assess the generalizability of the current findings.

Another key limitation of the present study is the lack of independence among the intervention conditions, as the interventions were implemented in a layered rather than isolated manner. Specifically, the gamification condition was coupled with high economic incentives, making it difficult to disentangle the individual effects of gamification from those of monetary rewards. Similarly, the nudging component overlapped with the gamification intervention, further complicating the attribution of observed effects to specific mechanisms. As a result, the effects of each intervention can be interpreted only relative to each other, rather than independently. Future studies may consider employing a factorial design that systematically varies and isolates each intervention component to allow for more precise causal inferences.

Furthermore, the lack of a control group and randomization limits the internal validity of the study, as other factors such as ease of use and satisfaction (Assemi et al., 2018), socio-demographic characteristics (Zegras et al., 2018), simplicity of user interactions, and installation barriers (Zhou et al., 2025) can affect participation irrespective of the interventions. Unfortunately, the app we used did not allow parallel groups with different conditions. Therefore, we chose a longitudinal study design in which participants were compared to themselves between a “control” (pre-intervention) and “experimental” period in which the intervention was introduced. In addition, we statistically controlled for the effect of at least some confounding factors in the models. However, we acknowledge that we cannot determine how the interventions would perform if compared to a baseline condition without any incentives or that there might be other confounders that impacted the results (e.g., car ownership, household composition, income, etc.). Parallel groups, in combination with randomization instead of a longitudinal design as applied in this study, may provide stronger counterfactual evidence of the causal effects.

Also, the present analysis assumes that trip underreporting primarily stems from motivational factors, such as forgetfulness or lack of engagement. However, some unrecorded trips may have resulted from technical issues with the app (e.g., if the app crashes during trip recording) or due to poor or missing GPS signal. In particular, if the GPS signal disappears near the place where the respondent starts or ends a trip, it may appear as a spatially unchained trip, even though the respondents correctly recorded two consecutive trips. Due to this, the overall rate of unreported trips may be somewhat overestimated. Unfortunately, distinguishing between these two sources of underreporting – motivational and technical – is inherently challenging. To limit the effect of GPS inaccuracies in the start and end locations of the trips, we considered a relatively generous buffer distance in the definition of spatially chained trips. In this way, even trips that did not immediately overlap in location were considered chained. To account for issues with app performance, user satisfaction with the app was included as a covariate in the analyses, under the assumption that lower satisfaction might indicate greater exposure to technical difficulties. However, satisfaction was not a significant predictor of the risk of trip underreporting in any of the models, nor did it moderate the intervention effects. One possible explanation is missing data and self-selection: respondents who experienced participation to be too burdensome may have been discouraged from participation (Assemi et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2025). Some of those were not included in the analyses, for example, because they did not fill out the Mid-term survey. The implication of this problem is that we cannot determine whether the interventions would be effective for people prone to early disengagement

(e.g., due to lower initial motivation or higher perceived burden) or to what extent the interventions can increase motivation in the presence of higher burden.

Finally, while this study examined interventions aimed at increasing participant motivation to remain engaged during data collection, we were unable to assess systematically whether these interventions also influenced the motivation to agree to participate. Recruitment efforts varied across periods, and we lack complete records of dissemination activities to account for their effects. Future research could employ designs that systematically vary incentives while holding recruitment strategies constant to more precisely identify whether, and to what extent, incentives influence uptake.

5. Conclusions

This study provides an initial evaluation of interventions to improve the continuity of travel data collection over extended periods of time. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first to systematically assess and quantify the impact of continuous incentivization, both economic and gamified, on long-term GPS and app-based travel data collection, while also comparing these approaches with non-incentive-based methods such as nudging. The results indicate that continuous economic incentives hold promise to motivate participants to provide more complete data. In contrast, the effectiveness of gamification remains less well understood and appears to be context- and user-dependent. These insights underscore the need for further research into the design and targeting of gamified elements in travel surveys. While the nudging in the current study was simplistic and was shown to be ineffective, more elaborate and tailored messaging may result in better outcomes. Overall, the study contributes to knowledge on participant engagement strategies that can improve long-term travel data collection and support evidence-based transport policy and planning.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anita Lyubanova: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fariya Sharmeen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors are unable or have chosen not to specify which data has been used.

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